

ФИЛИАЛ РОССИЙСКОГО
ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО
УНИВЕРСИТЕТА НЕФТИ И ГАЗА
(СНИУ) ИМЕНИ И.М. ГУБКИНА

ISSN 2181-1482

DOI JOURNAL 10.26739/2181-1482

ИННОВАЦИИ В НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ

ТОМ 4, НОМЕР 1

INNOVATION IN THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 1

ТАШКЕНТ-2023

ИННОВАЦИИ В НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ INNOVATION IN THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY

№1 (2023) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-1482-2023-1>

Главный редактор | Chief Editor:

МАГРУПОВ АБДУЛЛА МАХМУДОВИЧ
заместитель директора – исполнительный директор
Филиала Российского государственного университета
нефти и газа (НИУ) имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

Технический редактор | Technical Editor:

МАХМУДОВА ШАХНОЗА АБДУВАЛИЕВНА
Заведующий кафедрой «Общепрофессиональные
дисциплины» Филиала Российского государственного
университета нефти и газа (НИУ) имени И.М. Губкина в
г. Ташкенте

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ ЖУРНАЛ ИННОВАЦИИ В НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ EDITORIAL BOARD OF THE JOURNAL INNOVATION IN THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY

МИРСАЙТОВ МИРЗИЁД МИРОЗОДОВИЧ

кандидат технических наук,
заместитель директора по научным работам
и инновациям Филиала Российского
государственного университета нефти и газа (НИУ)
имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

ХАИРОВА ДИНАРА РИМОВНА

кандидат экономических наук,
профессор кафедры
"Экономика нефти и газа" Филиала
Российского государственного
университета нефти и газа (НИУ) имени
И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

КАДЫРБЕКОВА ДУРДОНА ХИКМАТУЛЛАЕВНА

доктор философии (PhD) по филологическим
наукам, доцент кафедры
"Иностранные языки Филиала
Российского государственного
университета нефти и газа (НИУ)
имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

ХАШАЕВ МУСЛИМ МУСАГИТОВИЧ

доктор философии (PhD), доцент
отделения «Физика, электротехника и
теплотехника» Филиала Российского
государственного университета нефти и газа
(НИУ) имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

АКРАМОВ БАХШИЛЛО ШАФИЕВИЧ

кандидат технических наук, профессор
отделения разработки нефтяных, газовых
и газоконденсатных месторождений Филиала
Российского государственного университета нефти
и газа (НИУ) имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

ГАФУРОВ КАМОЛ НУРИЛХАКОВИЧ

кандидат экономических наук, Заместитель
директора по учебной работе Филиала Российского
Государственного Университета нефти и газа (НИУ) им.
И.М.Губкина в г. Ташкенте

МИРСОЛИЕВА МУХАББАТХОН ТУХТАСИНОВНА

первый заместитель директора по вопросам молодёжи и
духовно-просветительской работе Филиала Российского
государственного университета нефти и газа (НИУ)
имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

НУРАЛИЕВ АЛМУХАН КАЛПАКБАЕВИЧ

кандидат технических наук, доцент
Ташкентского Государственного
технического университета
имени И.А.Каримова

ГЛЕБОВА ЕЛЕНА ВИТАЛЬЕВНА

доктор технических наук,
профессор, заведующая кафедрой
Промышленной безопасности
и охраны окружающей среды
Российского государственного
университета нефти и газа
(НИУ) имени И. М. Губкина (г. Москва)

АЗИМОВ ДИЛМУРОД

доктор технических наук (DSc), профессор
Гавайского университета в Манао (США)

ЭШМАТОВ АЛИМЖОН ХАСАНОВИЧ

PhD, профессор факультета
«Математика и статистика»
Университета Толедо (США)

DESIGN-PAГEMAKER | ДИЗАЙН - ВЕРСТКА: ХУРШИД МИРЗАХМЕДОВ

КОНТАКТ РЕДАКЦИЙ ЖУРНАЛОВ. WWW.TADQIQOT.UZ

ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

EDITORIAL STAFF OF THE JOURNALS OF WWW.TADQIQOT.UZ

Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

1. Отто О.Э., Зиямахомедова Н.Ф.

ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ВОДОРОДНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН \ PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE HYDROGEN ECONOMY IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN \ ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИДА ВОДОРОД ИҚТИСОДИЁТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ.....5

2. Ахмедова Ш.К.

ЭФФЕКТИВНЫЕ ФОРМЫ ВНЕДРЕНИЯ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ МЕТОДОВ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ И УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЕМ НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА \ EFFECTIVE FORMS OF INTRODUCING INNOVATIVE METHODS OF ORGANIZING AND MANAGING AN ENTERPRISE IN THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY OF UZBEKISTAN \ O‘ZBEKISTON NEFT-GAZ SAN‘OATIDA KORXONANI TASHKIL ETISH VA BOSHQARISHNING INNOVACION USULLARINI YO‘QISHNING SAMARALI SHAKLLARI.....11

3. Махмуджонов М.М., Матякубова П.М., Кодирова Ш.А.

АНАЛИЗ МЕТРОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИК ГАЗОАНАЛИЗАТОРОВ И МЕТРОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ ФИЗИКО-ХИМИЧЕСКИХ ИЗМЕРЕНИЙ \ ANALYSIS OF METROLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF GAS ANALYZERS AND METROLOGICAL SUPPORT OF PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL MEASUREMENTS \ ФИЗИК-КИМЁВИЙ ЎЛЧАШЛАРИНИНГ МЕТРОЛОГИК ТАЪМИНОТИ ВА ГАЗ НАЛИЗАТОРЛАРИНИНГ МЕТРОЛОГИК ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКАЛАРИНИНГ ТАҲЛИЛИ...17

4. Вассер П.Н., Кадирбекова Д.Х.

НОВЫЙ ПОДХОД К ИЗУЧЕНИЮ ЯЗЫКА НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ СПЕЦИАЛЬНОСТИ \ NEW APPROACH OF LEARNING SPECIALISED LANGUAGE OF OIL AND GAS \ NEFT VA GAS SOHASI TILINI URGANISHDA YANGI YONDASHUV.....24

5. Скулкова И.Н., Абдурахманов Р.А.

МЕДИЦИНСКИЕ РЕКОМЕНДАЦИИ И ПРОТИВОПОКАЗАНИЯ ПРИ ЗАНЯТИЯХ ФИЗИЧЕСКИМИ УПРАЖНЕНИЯМИ И ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ДРУГИХ СРЕДСТВ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ ПРИ МИОПИИ \ JISMONIY MASHQLAR PAYTIDA TIBBIY TAVSIYALAR VA KONTRENDIKACIYALAR VA MIYORI UCHUN BOSHQA JISMONIY MADANIYAT VOSITALARIDAN FOYDALANISH \ MEDICAL RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONTRAINDICATIONS FOR PHYSICAL EXERCISES AND THE USE OF OTHER MEANS OF PHYSICAL CULTURE IN MYOPIA.....30

6. Жабборов С.С., Мамаджанов Э.У.

ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ МЕТОДА БУРЕНИЯ С УПРАВЛЯЕМЫМ ДАВЛЕНИЕМ \ APPLICATION OF THE PRESSURE-CONTROLLED DRILLING METHOD \ BOSHQARILADIGAN BO 'ZIMLI BURG' ULLASH USULINI QO 'LLASH.....34

7. Мусаева Ф.М.

ВАЖНОСТЬ АНАЛИЗА ПОТРЕБНОСТЕЙ СТУДЕНТОВ НЕФТЕГАЗОВОГО ВУЗА ПРИ СОЗДАНИИ УЧЕБНЫХ МАТЕРИАЛОВ \ IMPORTANCE OF NEED ANALYSIS IN CREATING TEACHING MATERIALS FOR OIL AND GAS STUDENTS \ NEFT VA GAZ UNIVERSITETI TALABALARI UCHUN O‘QUV MATERIALLARINI YARATISHDA ENTIYOJ TAHLILINING AHAMIYATI.....39

8. Алимов М.А., Вохидов О.Ф.

ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ДАТЧИКА ХОЛЛА ДЛЯ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ КОЛИЧЕСТВА ПРИМЕСИ, СОДЕРЖАЩЕЙСЯ В ФЛЮИДАХ И НАХОДЯЩЕЙСЯ В ПЛАСТЕ \ APPLICATIONS OF THE HALL SENSOR TO DETERMINE THE AMOUNT \ OF IMPURITIES IN THE OIL IN THE RESERVOIR \ N YER OSTI QATLAMLARIDA JOYLASHGAN UGLEVODORODLAR TARKIBIDAGI YOT ELEMENTLARNING MIQDORINI ANIQLASHDA HOLL DATCHIKLARIDAN FOYDALANISH.....43

9. Маджитова О.М.

ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ НА ЗАНЯТИЯХ ПО АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ ДЛЯ СТУДЕНТОВ НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ \ THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING TECHNOLOGY IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE CLASSROOMS FOR STUDENTS OIL AND GAS \ NEFT VA GAZ SOHASI TALABALARINING INGLIZ TILI DARSLARIDA TEXNOLOGIYADAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGI.....48

10. Усманова А.А., Туймуродова Н.М.,

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНЫХ НАВЫКОВ И УРОВНЯ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ СТУДЕНТОВ ДЛЯ НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ \ FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL SKILLS AND THE LEVEL OF COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS FOR THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY \ ТАЛАБАЛАРИНИНГ НЕФТ ВА ГАЗ САНОАТИ УЧУН КАСБИЙ КЎНИКМАЛАРИНИ ВА МАЛАКА ДАРАЖАСИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ.....57

**ТЕЗИСЫ ПОБЕДИТЕЛЕЙ СТУДЕНЧЕСКОЙ
НАУЧНОЙ КОНФЕРЕНЦИИ "НЕФТЬ И ГАЗ -2023"**

1. Забарова Д.Т., Гуляев Д.Т.

КОМПЛЕКСНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ КОНТРОЛЯ КАЧЕСТВА ЦЕМЕНТИРОВАНИЯ И ТЕХНИЧЕСКОГО СОСТОЯНИЯ ОБСАЖЕННОГО СТВОЛА СКВАЖИНЫ \ OMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF CEMENTING QUALITY CONTROL AND THE TECHNICAL CONDITION OF A CASED WELLBORE.....62

2. Омонова Ф.Б., Мамарозиков Т.У.

МАГНИТНАЯ РАЗВЕДКА КАК ИНСТРУМЕНТ ДЛЯ ОБНАРУЖЕНИЯ ПОТЕНЦИАЛЬНЫХ АРХЕОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ОБЪЕКТОВ НА ЭТАПЕ ПОИСКОВЫХ РАБОТ \ MAGNETIC PROSPECTING AS A TOOL FOR DETECTING POTENTIAL ARCHAEOLOGICAL SITES DURING THE SEARCH PHASE.....65

3. Отажоннова Ш.Х., Мамарозиков Т.У.

ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ МЕТОДА ГРУППИРОВАНИЯ СЕЙСМОПРИЕМНИКОВ ДЛЯ ПОДАВЛЕНИЯ ПОВЕРХНОСТНОЙ ВОЛНЫ \ APPLICATION OF GEOPHONE GROUPING METHOD FOR SURFACE WAVE SUPPRESSION.....68

4. Наримов Д.Ш., Акрамов Б.Ш., Рябов С.С.

ВЫБОР ОПТИМАЛЬНОГО СПОСОБА ЭКСПЛУАТАЦИИ ДОБЫЧИ НЕФТИ В УСЛОВИЯХ ДЕФИЦИТА ЭЛЕКТРОЭНЕРГИИ \ CHOOSING THE OPTIMAL WAY TO OPERATE OIL PRODUCTION IN CONDITIONS OF ELECTRICITY SHORTAGE.....70

5. Добычина С.О., Рябов С.С.

ОБЗОР ВОЛОКОННО-ОПТИЧЕСКИХ ДАТЧИКОВ ДЛЯ ИЗМЕРЕНИЯ ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ В НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ \ OVERVIEW OF FIBER OPTIC SENSORS FOR TEMPERATURE MEASUREMENT IN THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY.....72

6. Рахимов С.Н., Ахмедов М.М.

ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКОГО СЕКТОРА УЗБЕКИСТАНА ПУТЕМ ВНЕДРЕНИЯ ВОЗОБНОВЛЯЕМЫХ ИСТОЧНИКОВ ЭНЕРГИИ И ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ИНДИВИДУАЛЬНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ ЭНЕРГООБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ \ OPTIMIZATION OF THE ENERGY SECTOR OF UZBEKISTAN THROUGH INTRODUCING RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES AND THE USE OF AN INDIVIDUAL ENERGY SUPPLY SYSTEM.....74

7. Жабборов С.С., Мамаджанов Э.У.

ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ БИОПОЛИМЕРНЫХ МИКРОСФЕР В МЕСТОРОЖДЕНИЯХ УЗБЕКИСТАНА \ THE POSSIBILITY OF USING BIOPOLYMER MICROSPHERES IN THE FIELDS OF UZBEKISTAN.....77

Мусаева Ф.М.Филиал РГУ нефти и газа (НИУ)
имени И.М.Губкина в г.Ташкенте,
старший преподаватель**ВАЖНОСТЬ АНАЛИЗА ПОТРЕБНОСТЕЙ СТУДЕНТОВ
НЕФТЕГАЗОВОГО ВУЗА ПРИ СОЗДАНИИ УЧЕБНЫХ МАТЕРИАЛОВ** <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7994330>**АННОТАЦИЯ**

Анализ потребностей на подготовительном этапе и в процессе реализации курса обучения английскому языку для специальных целей является основой достижения требуемых результатов по иностранному языку. Основным содержанием исследования является анализ потребностей студентов в нефтегазовой сфере, его значение в создании учебных материалов для дальнейшего развития будущих специалистов. В статье представлены результаты опросника, проведенного среди преподавателей-специалистов и студентов, а также анализ учебных планов преподавателей-специалистов. Анкетирование выполнялось студентами по направлению «Эксплуатация и обслуживание объектов транспорта и хранения нефти, газа и нефтепродуктов» и «Строительство и ремонт объектов системы трубопроводного транспорта», поэтому по результатам были выявлены некоторые наиболее часто используемые слова в этом направлении и определены темы для дальнейшей разработки учебно-методических материалов.

Ключевые слова: анализ, спрос учащихся, требования, тема урока, мнения участников, курс ESP.

Musaeva F.M.Branch of the Gubkin Russian
State University of Oil and Gas (NIU)
in Tashkent, senior lecturer**IMPORTANCE OF NEED ANALYSIS IN CREATING TEACHING MATERIALS FOR
OIL AND GAS STUDENTS****ANNOTATION**

Needs analysis at the preparatory stage and in the process of implementing the course of teaching English for special purposes, is the basis of achieving the required results in a foreign language. The main content of the research is the analysis of the needs of ESP students in Oil and gas field, its importance in creating lesson materials for the further development of the future specialists. The article presents the results of the survey conducted among the content-teachers and the students as well as the analysis of the content-teachers' syllabi. The questionnaire was accomplished by the students in the direction of "Operation and maintenance of transport and storage facilities for oil, gas

and refined products” and “Construction and repair of pipeline transport system facilities”, so according to the results, some most-used words in this direction have been found and the topics for the further development of the teaching materials have been identified.

Key words: analysis, students’ demand, requirements, the theme of the lesson, participants’ views, ESP course.

Musayeva F. M.

I.M. Gubkin nomidagi Rossiya
davlat neft va gaz universitetining (NIU)
Toshkent shahridagi filiali, katta o‘qituvchi

NEFT VA GAZ UNIVERSITETI TALABALARI UCHUN O'QUV MATERIALLARINI YARATISHDA EHTIYOJ TAHLILINING AHAMIYATI

ANNOTATSIYA

Xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda kutilgan natijalarga erishish uchun maxsus maqsadlarda ingliz tilini o'qitish kursining dastlabki bosqichida ehtiyojlar tahlilini o'tkazish kutilgan natijalarga erishish uchun asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Mazkur tadqiqotning asosiy mazmuni talabalarning neft va gaz sohasiga bo'lgan ehtiyojlarini tahlil qilish, hamda tahlil natijalari asosida o'quv materiallarini yaratishdagi ahamiyati aks etadi. Maqolada mutaxassis o'qituvchilar va talabalar o'rtasida o'tkazilgan so'rovnoma natijalari, shuningdek, mutaxassis o'qituvchilarning o'quv dasturlari tahlili keltirilgan. So'rovnoma "neft va gaz mahsulotlarini transport qilish va saqlash ob'ektlarini ekspluatatsiya qilish va ularga xizmat ko'rsatish" va "gaz-neft quvurlari va gaz-neftni er ostida saqlash omborlarini qurish va ta'mirlash" yunalishida tahsil olayotgan talabalar bilan o'tkazildi, shu bois, natijalarga ko'ra, mazkur yo'nalishda eng ko'p qo'llaniladigan so'zlar aniqlandi, va o'quv materiallarini yanada rivojlantirish uchun mavzular belgilab olindi.

Kalit so'zlar: tahlil, talabalarning ehtiyojlari, talablar, dars mavzusi, ishtirokchilarning fikrlari, ESP kursi.

Introduction. Today modernity presents ever higher requirements for learning and practical mastery of foreign languages in everyday communication and professional sphere. Due to the globalization processes of professional communication, the development of scientific cooperation and the modernization of the education system, teaching of ESP (English for Special Purposes) is becoming important and a challenge for many professionals in the field. In accordance with the provisions of modern educational standards, graduates of non-linguistic specialties are required to master all types of speech activity, interpretation and translation, listening, as well as lexical and grammatical skills for the successful implementation of professional and scientific activities.

In many cases the level of language competence of students of non-linguistic specialties and training areas does not always meet the requirements. The significant factor of dealing with this issue is to find out the needs of the learners, in favour of innovative methodological techniques aimed at developing the skills of professionally oriented communication in a foreign language. This raises the problem of rethinking the existing methods of teaching English for special purposes.

Theoretical aspects of ESP teaching, as well as the problems faced by practicing ESP teachers, are widely represented by foreign researchers (T. Dudley-Evans, A. Waters, T. Hutchinson, G. Ferguson, K. Hyland, N. Hess, and others). [4, 5, 6, 7, 8]. Among Uzbek researchers, involved in the implementation of ESP, it should be noted the works of M.A. Yusupova, S.A. Aminova, A. Ashirbayeva, A.S. Baisov, dedicated to the importance of teaching approaches in ESP sphere. [1, 2, 9].

Discussing the conditions for the successful implementation of a professionally oriented language course, the founders of the modern profile-oriented approach in teaching T. Hutchinson and A. Waters note that it can be accomplished by a thorough study of the needs and requests of students.

The researchers state that the difference between English for Special Purposes and a general English course is not “only the existence of a need, but rather awareness of this need” [6, p. 11].

Burksaitiene (2008) [3, p. 274] claims that needs analysis is a tool to gather participants’ views in teaching ESP. Dudley-Evans also noted that the principal aim of the ESP course is to meet the explicit needs of the learners. Scientists come to the conclusion that the content of the course (Science, Medicine, Business, Tourism) is secondary to its main characteristic - the ability to successfully determine the need to learn English for Special Purposes. [4]

Analysis. Before the creation of each lesson materials, the important thing was to identify the topic of the lesson, so it should correspond with the students’ special subjects as it is a significant factor for the students to be familiar with the theme of the lesson in their native language. In this regard, content-teachers’ syllabi was analysed. The following themes were in the curriculum: corrosion protection, designing pipeline systems, technological reliability of main pipelines, pumps and compressors, compressor stations, storage facilities for oil and petroleum products, energy-saving gas transport technologies etc.

Moreover, during the research students’ demand was also needed. So, keeping this point, some researchers’ works were analysed. Hutchinson and Waters stated [7, p. 181] that ESP should be based on the learners’ demands for learning that means teachers’ actions cover everything from content to method. Another point of view about satisfying the requirements of ESP teaching claims that the core of ESP is to discover the required learning contexts of learners. Considering that they are learners who study a specific field, this must be realized by the needs of these learners. This correspondence is fulfilled with Needs Analysis (NA). [4]

Considering above-mentioned points, needs analysis (what the learner needs to do in the target situation) was done. The main goal was to find out the students’ interest in the subject that they study. Needs Analysis was accomplished with the second, third and four year of students in the direction of “Operation and maintenance of transport and storage facilities for oil, gas and refined products” and “Construction and repair of pipeline transport system facilities”. 48 students’ responses were received. The questions of the needs analysis were:

- What topic would you like to discuss during the English lesson?
- What topics do find the most interesting in your sphere?
- Outline the themes that would be useful for you in the future.

5. Какие темы, по Вашему мнению, помогут вам развиваться в вашем специфическом направлении в будущем? Напишите некоторые из них.

48 ответов

Pipes and pipelines

Строение трубопровода. Коррозия металлов.

Pipes and Pipelines. Хотелось бы побольше информации на эту тему

Pipeline transportation

Pipes and pipelines.Petrochemicals

Pipeline transport, its classification. How does it useful?

Pipes and pipelines, safety first

The refinery. Хотелось бы больше информации на эту тему

According to the received answers, most students’ answers were the following topics: pipelines – 24 times, compressor stations – 22 times, storage – 18 times, safety – 12 times, pigging devices – 11 times, crude oil – 9 times, problems and solutions – 9 times, gas turbine units – 8 times. There were other themes, but their occurrence was no more than 3 times, so the topics were not considered as important as those ones. When the topics of the lesson were clear, it was important to

compare the topics suggested by the students and the topics that were in the teachers' syllabi. As it was expected the topics were similar. Those themes were developed as teaching materials for the "Operation and maintenance of transport and storage facilities for oil, gas and refined products" and "Construction and repair of pipeline transport system facilities".

Conclusion. Thus, we have considered the value of needs analysis and objectives for the course, considering how content-teachers' as well as the students' contribution can serve as a source in decision-making process about what should be included in the lesson materials during the lesson. ESP students are usually adults who have already learned the basics of the English language and have some knowledge of professional subjects that ESP teachers may not be familiar with. Students need knowledge of the language in order to master professional communication skills. ESP focuses on language that is used in a real professional context rather than teaching grammar structures and vocabulary that is not related to students' core subjects. The content of the ESP must be integrated into the subject area, current or future professional activities of students. While considering received results, the content of the lesson, texts and various linguistic elements should be carefully studied. In addition, it is necessary to choose effective teaching methods; educational materials; the degree to which certain skills must be acquired.

References:

1. Aminova S.A, Umida J., the use of methods of teaching foreign language process, Academic Research in Educational Sciences, Vol. 2, CSPI Conference 2., 2021, p. 1918-1921.
2. Baisov A.S., Innovative Technologies in Teaching Foreign languages, Academic Research in Educational Sciences, Vol. 2, CSPI Conference 2., 2021, p.287-292.
3. Burkšaitienė, N., University students' attitudes towards the usage of WEB 2.0 tools for learning ESP. A Preliminary investigation, Societal studies, 10.13165/SMS-15-7-2-07, 2015, p. 270-291.
4. Dudley-Evans T., St John M. J. Developments in English for Specific Purposes. A multi-disciplinary approach. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1998.
5. Ferguson, G. 1994. Classnotes of the course «Teaching English for Specific Purposes». Instituto for Applied Language Studies. The University of Edinburgh. P.32
6. Hess N., English for academic purposes: Teacher development in a demanding arena, Volume 16, Issue 1, 1997, p. 15-26.
7. T. Hutchinson and A. Waters, English for Specific Purposes, Cambridge University Press, 1987, pp. 183.
8. Hyland K., ESP and Writing, The Handbook of English for Specific Purposes, Edited by Brian Paltridge and Sue Starfield 2013, pp. 570.
9. Yuldasheva M., Methodology of teaching English for specific purposes and difference between general English, European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences, Vol. 8 No. 1, ISSN 2056-5852, 2020, pp. 128.

ФИЛИАЛ РОССИЙСКОГО
ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО
УНИВЕРСИТЕТА НЕФТИ И ГАЗА
(НИУ) ИМЕНИ И.М. ГУБКИНА

ИННОВАЦИИ В НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ

ТОМ 4, НОМЕР 1

INNOVATION IN THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 1

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,

Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Тадқиқот город Ташкент,

улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000